

Effects of Climate Change on Medium-Pressure Insulator Insulation and Network Stability

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Abstract

Electrical losses are an unacceptable phenomenon in the power grid, especially the distribution grid, which has increased in recent years due to climate change in the southern regions of the country (such as reduced rainfall, water shortages, increased internal and external dust sources, and high air humidity). Among them, one of the equipment's that has been affected greatly under these conditions and has consequently increased technical losses and unwanted outages in the distribution network is insulators, and therefore, the technical investigation and evaluation of how these problems occur and their prediction can be of great help to engineers in designing and selecting the correct insulator for such regions. Therefore, in this article, the climate of the hot and dry regions of southern Iran (a case study of Khuzestan province) was first described, and then, in order to investigate the effects of the region's climatic conditions on silicon and ceramic medium-pressure insulators, two parameters, dust and relative air humidity, were selected. Also, insulators isolated from the network with different pollution levels were used and then subjected to laboratory tests, which included leakage current and insulator surface resistance. Finally, the modeling of the contaminated insulator was carried out using EMTP software. The results obtained from this paper indicate that the current insulators installed in the network were suitable for the conditions before the climate change of recent years and have lost their efficiency in the network and are now one of the main reasons for the increase in electrical losses and reliability of the distribution network. The results of the simulations also indicate the high accuracy of insulator modeling in polluted and desert conditions and can be used in network analyses.

Keywords: Electrical losses - Climate change - Silicon and ceramic insulators - Insulator modeling - EMTP software.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main equipment's in the power grid (generation, transmission and distribution) are insulators, which are responsible for isolating energy lines from other parts, and the main reason for outages in the power grid is mainly the occurrence of errors in the network insulation. Under normal conditions, insulators have high electrical resistance and low insulation loss coefficient, and therefore their leakage currents are very low and negligible, but their performance and efficiency are always affected by environmental factors because they are mainly installed in open space. These factors vary in different regions and are always one of the indicators that are considered in selecting the correct insulator. However, in recent years, the phenomenon of drought and rapid climate changes in general have disrupted engineering calculations and have severely reduced the efficiency of insulators and ultimately the network. Relatively many studies have been conducted on insulators and the effects of climatic conditions on them, of course, each of them was based on the specific climate of those regions [1].

The profound and multifaceted challenges posed by climate change resulting from global warming and climate change have increasingly attracted the attention of the international community [2-3]. The Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) paints a clear picture and documents a

significant increase in global surface temperature. According to the report, from 1850–1900 to 2001–2020, global surface temperature increased by 0.99°C, and by 1.09°C from 2011–2020 compared to 1850–1900 [4]. This increase, as explained by various climate models [5], is expected to strengthen the hydrological cycle and cause uneven global distribution of precipitation. Evaporation rates are expected to increase with increasing temperatures, potentially outpacing increases in precipitation and exacerbating drought risks, particularly in water-scarce regions. Since the mid-20th century, the frequency and severity of droughts have increased in many parts of Africa, East Asia, and South Asia, affecting agriculture and wildlife ecosystems [6]. Climate change and drought affect various parts of human life [7], and the electricity industry is very important due to its special role in providing electricity. The electricity industry uses generation, super-distribution and distribution networks to transmit energy to consumers, which include long lines, towers and insulators [8]. It should be noted that one of the results of climate change and drought is an increase in the amount of fine dust and dust. With the occurrence of wind, fine dust settles on the electricity network and the insulators of the electricity transmission lines, reducing their insulating power and causing faults in the electricity network and ultimately disconnecting the network [9]. Therefore, it is very important to investigate the effect of dust particles on network insulators.

Reference [10] examined laboratory techniques for simulating contamination on the surface of high-voltage insulators under different weather conditions. In this study, the contamination of insulators was carried out according to the IEC60815 standard [11], and a room called a fog chamber was introduced to place the insulators and conduct laboratory tests. In this room, it was possible to control humidity and temperature using the equipment installed in it. In another study, the leakage current on the surface of silicone insulators in contaminated and cold fog conditions was investigated. Among the results of this study was the occurrence of severe coronas due to the presence of contamination and cold fog. In addition, it was observed that the surface resistance of the insulator is greatly reduced by the application of fog, which causes an increase in the leakage current [12-13]. In [14], a method based on the frequency components of the leakage current was presented to determine the contamination level on insulators, which yielded very interesting results. Also, in continuation of these studies, a method was presented in the field of the relationship between the harmonic characteristics of the leakage current and the location of contamination in the chain of high-voltage porcelain insulators, which helps to locate the location of contamination to some extent [15].

Reference [16] analyzed the effects of dust accumulation on 33 kV line insulators. In this paper, the types of dust used in this experiment include cement dust, sea salt, local dust and urea dust. According to IEC 60507 standard, the insulator samples were contaminated by artificial means. After contamination, the samples were left unattended for 24 hours to dry naturally. This experimental procedure was continued for 7 days until significant and visible contamination was obtained on the surface of each insulator. The results obtained in this process are a clear indication that salt and urea contamination affect porcelain and polymer insulators more. In an attempt to compare, it was observed that cement contamination does not have a significant effect on porcelain and polymer insulators. The maximum leakage currents associated with urea contamination and salt contamination are higher because urea can reabsorb water molecules. The results also showed that polymer insulators have a higher breakdown voltage than porcelain insulators. Relatively, the effect of contamination on porcelain insulators is greater than that on polymer insulators. Salt, cement and urea contaminations have a greater effect on porcelain insulators than polymer insulators. The breakdown voltage of polymer insulators in salt contamination is 17% higher than that of porcelain insulators, the breakdown voltage of polymer insulators in cement contamination is 22% higher than that of porcelain insulators, and the breakdown voltage of polymer insulators in porcelain insulators is 31% higher than that of polymer insulators.

But in continuation of these studies, this article examines the effects of environmental parameters specific to the south of the country, namely air humidity (northern) and dust on insulators used in the 33 kV network (silicone and ceramic), and in addition to laboratory tests, electrical modeling of insulators in the presence of dust particles is performed with EMTP software. In general, the first part examines the hot and dry climate (a case study of the Khuzestan region) and the changes in important indicators with statistical results of different years are expressed. In the second part, laboratory measurements and electrical indicators are discussed, in the third part, insulator modeling in polluted conditions is explained with the help of EMTP software, and at the end, conclusions and evaluation of the results obtained are discussed.

2. SOUTHERN CLIMATE OF THE IRAN COUNTRY

Drought is a common phenomenon in countries located in subtropical latitudes such as Iran. In these regions, where the most deserts in the world are present, drought is a normal and may occur in any location and have undesirable consequences, and the effects of drought such as its intensity, duration and magnitude vary from place to place. In the climatic classification, Khuzestan province is known as an arid and semi-arid climate (Figure 1), and its proximity to the deserts of northern Arabia, eastern Syria and southern Iraq on the other hand has caused it to become a center of dust storms in the country. In recent years, climate change and successive droughts, increasing and unprincipled use of water resources have caused the spread of these storms. These changes have led to an increase in temperature, a decrease in soil moisture and the loss of vegetation, which has led to the formation of new centers that, in addition to increasing the frequency of dust storms, have increased the concentration, duration and distance of transmission from the source area [8]. Figure 2 shows the maximum dust levels measured by meteorological instruments from 1380 to 1395, which has been increasing and in recent years, 10,000 micrograms per square meter has been recorded, which is the highest level that the instruments are capable of measuring. These results indicate extremely polluted air in these areas. Figure 3 also shows the curve for the minimum and maximum ambient humidity by month of the year, with the minimum being 30 and the maximum being 93 percent. The combination of these conditions can create a conductive layer on insulators and cause short circuits in distribution lines.

Figure 1. Climatic zoning of Khuzestan Province in 1403 [17]

Figure 2. Graph of pollution volume over a 15-year period [17]

Figure 3. Annual humidity chart in percentages [17]

3. LABORATORY TESTS

In general, it can be said that the outcome of all environmental factors affecting insulators can be measured by the leakage current index, and an insulator whose leakage current index does not change much is considered suitable. For this purpose, in this article, laboratory tests were conducted on two types of widely used insulators in the 33 kV network, namely silicon and ceramic insulators (Figure 4), and their leakage current index was tested. However, according to the contents of the first section, it is necessary to carefully select the environmental parameters affecting the performance of insulators and their range of changes so that the tests can be carried out accordingly. Therefore, the environmental indicators studied were hot air humidity (so-called sultry air) and dust suspended in the air, and the rate of its changes was categorized as Table 1. The first condition is related to a clean insulator, meaning that the insulator is in factory conditions or after rain, which leads to the surface of the insulator being cleaned. The second condition indicates common and common environmental conditions that are lightly polluted due to pollutants (such as car exhaust fumes, etc.), and the third condition indicates the severe amount of dust that is created due to droughts and climate changes and settles on the surface of the insulators. It is noted that in agricultural areas, chemical fertilizers and in industrial areas (industrial pollutants) cause other pollution on the insulating surfaces, which are ignored in this article. On the other hand, all the mentioned cases are carried out in three humidity ranges, where the first (30 percent) and the last (93 percent) are the lowest and highest relative humidity levels in Khuzestan province, respectively, and the second (52 percent) is the average value of the mentioned index.

Table 1- Classification of different environmental conditions

Amount of pollution \ Humidity level	Pollution-free insulator	Lightly contaminated insulator	Insulator with heavy contamination
Light (30%)	✓	✓	✓
Medium (52%)	✓	✓	✓
Heavy (93%)	✓	✓	✓

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Examples of insulators tested in the laboratory a) Ceramic insulator b) Silicon insulator

3-1- Laboratory Setup

To measure the leakage current, a circuit according to Figure 5-a was used, which allows the measurement of the leakage current with the help of a resistance divider. The relevant laboratory circuit is also shown in Figure 5-b. In measuring the leakage current at each stage (Table 1), the insulator is placed in a glass chamber and the amount of ambient humidity and dust on the insulator surface is adjusted, and then the insulator is subjected to high voltage. Since the network under study is 33 kV, the measurement should be made at this voltage, but in practice, in order to compensate for the voltage drop caused by high load, this voltage is usually around 38 kV. Therefore, in this study, in order to consider the worst conditions, a value of 40 kV was considered and the

tests were carried out at this voltage. After measuring the leakage current, the surface resistance of the insulators was measured in each of the above conditions.

Figure 5: Test Circuit (a) Schematic of a high-voltage circuit for measuring leakage current of silicon and ceramic insulators (b) Laboratory circuit for insulator leakage current test

3-2- Laboratory results

The main cause of leakage current changes is the creation of a layer of contaminants on the insulator surface, which consequently reduces the surface resistance and insulating properties of the insulator. Although the resistance of insulators (clean insulators) is usually very high, this value can change significantly with changes in environmental conditions, and consequently increase the leakage current. Figures 6-a and 6-b show the graphs of the leakage current of silicone and ceramic insulators at a voltage of 40 kV. As can be seen, its amount has increased sharply due to the increase in dust. So that the leakage current of silicone insulators in a clean state is 20 microamperes, but this amount reaches 85 microamperes, which is more than 4 times under conditions of heavy pollution and high humidity. This is different for ceramic insulators, where the value ranges from 200 microamperes to 2300 microamperes, which is more than 10 times higher.

Figure 6. Leakage current of a (a) silicon insulator and (b) Ceramic insulator

Figures 7-a and 7-b also show the surface resistance graphs of silicon and ceramic insulators, respectively, showing that the increase in dust has greatly reduced the insulation resistance, so that the resistance of the ceramic insulator in the worst case, i.e., the presence of high humidity and dust, is reduced to about 17 megaohms, which is very inappropriate.

Figure 7. Surface resistance of (a) silicon insulator and (b) ceramic insulator

3. ELECTRICAL MODELING OF INSULATOR IN THE PRESENCE OF CONTAMINATION AND CORONA

In this section, electrical modeling of insulator in the presence of dust is examined. This model consists of two parts, which are:

- 1) Clean insulator model
- 2) Contamination and flashover model on insulator surface

To model clean insulator in this article, the parallel RC model has been used, which is a common and common model in insulator simulation. In this model, which is simulated in EMTP software (Figure 8), the resistance R indicates the ohmic resistance of the insulator and C also indicates the capacitance of the insulator. Typically, the value of R is very high (about a few hundred megaohms) and C also has a small capacitance of about a few picocoulombs. To model contamination, a 3R resistor is used, and to simulate creep voltage, a Flashover Switch element is used along with a 1C capacitor, and the entire set is connected in series with the 3R resistor.

1 AC is a high-voltage voltage source, 1R is a limiting resistor that is responsible for limiting the current in the event of a short circuit, and 2R is a measuring resistor that measures the insulator's leakage current.

Figure 8. Circuit related to the modeled contaminated insulator in EMTP software

Figure 9 shows the experimental results and simulation of the leakage current of the silicon insulator in the voltage range of 0-40 kV for two clean and contaminated states. As can be seen, the results obtained in the

clean state almost coincide with each other, but in the contaminated state there is a slight tolerance. This is probably due to the occurrence of creep and sudden changes in the leakage current.

Figure 9: Leakage current curves of silicone insulators for two clean and contaminated states (laboratory) and the curves obtained for the same two states using a software model

4. CONCLUSION

In this article, the electrical parameters of silicone and ceramic insulators, which are the most widely used insulators for 33 kV lines, were examined, and the leakage current and electrical resistance indices of the insulators were evaluated through laboratory measurements and software modeling. The results obtained from this study are summarized as follows:

- 1) With the increase in the amount of dust from light to heavy, the leakage current increases sharply, and this greatly increases the line losses.
- 2) The measurements showed that the insulating power of silicone insulators is much higher than that of ceramic insulators, and under conditions of heavy contamination, its electrical resistance is also higher than that of ceramic insulators in the clean state and shows better stability.
- 3) Simulation results show that the contamination on the insulator surface can be modeled as a parallel resistance with the insulator and other details can be added to it.
- 4) Although the silicone materials used in the silicone insulator are also vulnerable to environmental conditions such as high temperatures and lead to other problems such as destruction of the slats, etc., they perform better compared to ceramic insulators and it is recommended that they be replaced with these insulators.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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